

STUDIES IN THE CYCLOPENTANE SERIES. PART I. SYNTHESIS OF 1-METHYLCYCLOPENTANE-1 : 2-DI- CARBOXYLIC ACID IN *CIS*- AND *TRANS*-FORMS.*

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A new method has been developed for the synthesis of substituted *cyclopentane* rings and by this method 1-methyl-*cyclopentane*-1 : 2-dicarboxylic acid has been synthesised in *cis*- and *trans*-forms. Their stereochemical properties have been studied in detail and their analogy with the two forms of *cyclopentane*-1 : 2-dicarboxylic acids have been established.

This series of investigation was originally undertaken with a view to study the modes of formation and stereochemical properties of 1-methyl *cyclopentane*-1 : 2-dicarboxylic acid (I), so that ultimately Wieland's acid (II), obtained by the oxidation of sterol and bile acids (*Z. physiol. Chem.*, 1924, 134, 276), may be synthesised.

(I)

(II)

As a reference compound, the acid (I) has been prepared from ethyl 2-methyl*cyclopentane*-2-carboxylate by a method, which is, however, identical with that used by Linstead in the preparation of the corresponding *cyclohexane* analogue. Ethyl 2-methyl*cyclopentane*-2-carboxylate has been converted into the cyanohydrin (III) with liquid hydrocyanic acid and this, on dehydration with thionyl chloride and pyridine, gives the unsaturated ester (IV, R=CN) (containing much dissolved sulphur, which is removed by boiling with precipitated copper in benzene solution.) It undergoes hydrolysis to the unsaturated acid (IV, R=COOH) and this, on reduction with sodium amalgam gives only the *trans*-form of the acid (I), m. p. 142°.

(III)

(IV)

* A preliminary note appeared in *Science and Culture*, 1940, 6, 560.

Attention was then directed to its synthesis from open-chain compounds with the proper substituents. β -Ethoxyethyl iodide has been condensed with sodioacetoacetic ester to give ethyl γ -ethoxyacetobutyrate and this on hydrolysis gives γ -ethoxypropylmethyl ketone (V). The cyanohydrin of the latter is condensed with sodiocyanoacetic ester (Thorpe and Higson, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1906, **89**, 1455) and the ethoxydicyano-ester (VI) is isolated as a viscous liquid.

The latter (VI) has also been prepared in a very good yield by the addition of hydrogen cyanide to ethyl α -cyano β -(γ -ethoxypropyl)-crotonate (*cf.* Hope and Sheldon, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1922, **121**, 2226; Cope, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1937, **59**, 2327).

Attempted cyclisation of (VI) to (I) by heating with fuming hydrochloric acid furnishes a chlorinated acid instead of the desired cyclopentane-acid. Simonsen (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1909, **95**, 1171) converted methoxymethylene-dimalonic ester into cyclobutane-1 : 3-dicarboxylic acid.

The hydrolysis of CN in (VI) to carbethoxy did not prove successful. But (VI) gives after hydrolysis and esterification, ethyl α -methyl- α -(γ -ethoxypropyl)-succinate.

Ethyl δ -bromo- α -carbethoxyvalerate (*Biochem. Z.*, 1930, **226**, 228) has been hydrolysed with hydrobromic acid and the semi-solid mass, so obtained, is treated with thionyl chloride and brominated *in situ* and ethyl $\alpha\delta$ -dibromovalerate (VII, R=H), after interaction with sodiocyanoacetic ester gives (VIII) in very good yield, which has been obtained by Fuson (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1938, **60**, 1237) in a different manner. On hydrolysis it gives crude *trans*-cyclopentane-1 : 2-dicarboxylic acid and the conversion of the *cis*-form has been accomplished through its anhydride (Perkin, *loc. cit.*).

Similarly, from ethyl methylmalonate and trimethylene bromide, ethyl γ -bromopropylmethylmalonate has been isolated in moderate yield. The latter, on hydrolysis with hydrobromic acid, gives the corresponding bromo-acid (*i.e.* γ -bromopropyl methyl malonic acid), probably contaminated with the related lactone. On treatment with phosphorus pentabromide and bromine and subsequent addition of alcohol, ethyl $\alpha\delta$ -dibromo- α -methyl valerate (VII, R=Me) has been isolated. This on treatment with sodio-cyanoacetic ester gives the corresponding *cyclopentanecyano-ester* (IX) in 89% yield. It is hydrolysed with concentrated hydrochloric acid to the pure *trans*-acid (I), m.p. 143°.

It may be noted that the appearance of the contiguous carboxyl groups in *cycloparaffin* dibasic acids assume *cis*- configuration in *cyclobutane* series (Perkin, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1894, 65, 583), a mixture of *cis*- and *trans*-forms in *cyclohexane* series (*cf.* Fuson, *loc. cit.*), and *trans*-configuration in the *cyclopentane* series, which is of particular interest in this investigation.

When the cyano-ester (X) is heated in a sealed tube with concentrated hydrochloric acid, it is hydrolysed and decarboxylated to a mixture of *cis*- and *trans*-*cyclopentane* acids (I). The crude product is treated with acetic anhydride, whereby the anhydride of the *cis*-acid is obtained as a gelatinous mass, b. p. 101°/4 mm., whence the *cis*-acid is obtained as clusters of small cubes, m.p. 124-26°. The range in m.p. indicates the partial formation of the anhydride. The *cis*- acid can also be obtained by heating the *trans*-acid with acetic anhydride and then distilling under reduced pressure, when a small amount of the anhydride is obtained as the distillate whence the acid can be isolated.

If the *trans*-acid is heated with hydrochloric acid at 190-200°, there is an appreciable conversion of the *trans*- into the *cis*- variety, but the reverse change can not be brought about. The method of analysis is, however, crude, depending mainly on the change in melting points and not on thermal analysis. Special interest attaches to the latter observation in connection with the synthesis of Wieland's tricarboxylic acid (II), where the carboxyl groups occupy *trans*-configuration.

It may be of interest to draw attention to the physical properties of the *trans*- and *cis*-*cyclopentane*-1-methyl-1:2-dicarboxylic acids with the isomeric forms of *cyclopentane*-1:2-dicarboxylic acids. The *cis*-variety crystallises in small cubes, m.p. 142°, whilst the *trans*-variety melts at 161° and crystallises in plates. The higher m.p. and lesser solubility are associated with the *trans*-acid, whilst lower m.p. and greater solubility in water are the properties of the *cis*-acid in this series as in others, such as *cis*- and *trans*-*cyclopentane*-1:2-dicarboxylic acids.

Linstead has assigned definite structures to the two forms of *cyclohexane-1-methyl-1 : 2-dicarboxylic acids* from similar considerations of physical properties alone.

EXPERIMENTAL.

Ethyl 1-Methylcyclopentane-2-cyanohydrin-1-carboxylate (III).—Hydrocyanic acid, generated from potassium cyanide (37 g.) and dilute sulphuric acid (37 c.c. in 40 c.c. of water), was passed into well cooled methylcyclopentanone-carboxylic ester (25 g.), to which a drop of potassium cyanide solution was added as a condensing agent. After standing overnight at 0°, a few drops of ice-cold dilute sulphuric acid were added and a current of air blown through the liquid to remove excess of hydrocyanic acid gas. The mixture was diluted, extracted with ether, dried and distilled in vacuum after the addition of a drop of sulphuric acid, b.p. 122°/4 mm., yield 24 g. (Found : N, 6·7. $C_{12}H_{15}O_3N$ requires N, 7·1 per cent).

1-Methyl-1-carbethoxy-2-cyclopenten-2-nitrile (IV, R=CN).—To a cooled mixture of the cyanohydrin (24 g.) and pyridine (22 g.) was added thionyl chloride (17 g.) drop by drop. After standing overnight the mixture was heated on the steam-bath for 2 hours. The supernatant clear liquid was extracted with dry ether and the plastic mass left was decomposed with ice and then thoroughly extracted with ether. The combined ethereal extract was washed with acid and alkali, dried and distilled in vacuum. The distillate contained much sulphur, which was removed by refluxing with precipitated copper in benzene solution on the water-bath for 3 hours. After filtration, the solvent was removed off and the nitrile was distilled, b.p. 100-2°/4 mm., yield 13 g. (Found : N, 7·7. $C_{12}H_{13}O_2N$ requires N, 7·7 per cent).

1-Methyl- Δ^2 -cyclopenten-1 : 2-dicarboxylic Acid (IV, R=COOH).—The unsaturated nitrile (13 g.) was refluxed with fuming hydrochloric acid (20 c.c.) for 15 hours. The acid was extracted with a large excess of ether, in which, however, it was sparingly soluble. On removal of the solvent, the acid crystallised out in stout needles, m.p. 202°, which rose to 204° after recrystallisation from acetic acid. It is sparingly soluble in water, yield theoretical. (Found : C, 56·8 ; H, 5·7. $C_8H_{10}O_4$ requires, C, 56·48 ; H, 5·8 per cent).

trans-1-Methylcyclopentane-1 : 2-dicarboxylic Acid (I).—The unsaturated acid (V, 5 g.) was reduced with 10 times the theoretical quantity of 3% sodium amalgam in a slightly alkaline solution. The filtrate was acidified and thoroughly extracted with ether after saturation with sodium chloride. The oil, obtained after the removal of the solvent, solidified on standing and scratching. On repeated crystallisation from

water, it was obtained in small cubes, m.p. 142° , yield 2 g. (Found : C, 55.9; H, 6.9. $C_8H_{12}O_4$ requires C, 55.8; H, 6.9 per cent).

β -Ethoxyethyl-acetoacetic Ester (Ethyl γ -ethoxyacetobutyrate).—To a well-cooled solution of sodium ethoxide, prepared from sodium (8 g.) and alcohol (92 c.c.), was gradually added a mixture of ethoxyethyl iodide (97 g.) and ethyl acetoacetate (55 g.). The mixture was heated on the water-bath for 12 hours and then diluted with water, extracted with ether and washed with sodium bicarbonate and dried. The ester was obtained as a clear mobile liquid, b.p. $110-113^{\circ}/7$ mm., yield 50 g. (Found : C, 59.9; H, 8.7. $C_{10}H_{18}O_4$ requires C, 59.4; H, 8.9 per cent).

γ -Ethoxypropylmethyl Ketone (V).—The above ester (50 g.) was hydrolysed with sulphuric acid (8%, 400 c.c.) by boiling for 20 hours. On cooling, the solution was saturated with ammonium sulphate and extracted with ether. The ethereal extract was dried over calcium chloride and after removal of the solvent through a fractionating column, the ketone was finally obtained from the residue as a mobile liquid, b.p. 169° , yield 20 g. (Found : C, 64.8; H, 10.5. $C_7H_{14}O$ requires C, 64.6; H, 10.7 per cent).

Ethyl $\alpha\beta$ -Dicyano- β -(γ -ethoxypropyl)-butyrate (VI).—The ketone (20 g.), to which a drop of potassium cyanide had been added, was cooled in a freezing mixture. Hydrocyanic acid, generated from potassium cyanide (30 g.) and sulphuric acid (30 c.c. in 45 c.c. of water; was gradually passed into the ketone. After standing overnight at 0° , it was worked up in the usual way, when the cyanohydrin (19 g.) was obtained, b.p. $122^{\circ}/9$ mm. To a mixture of this cyanohydrin (17 g.) and dry alcohol (12 c.c.), cooled in a freezing mixture, was added with shaking, ice-cold alcoholic suspension of ethyl sodiocyanoacetate (prepared from 15 g. of ethyl cyanoacetate and 45 c.c. of alcohol). After standing for 3 days at ordinary temperature, the mixture was decomposed with ice and hydrochloric acid. The heavy oil was extracted with ether, washed with alkali and with water and finally dried. The dicyano-ester was obtained as a viscous liquid, b.p. $170-175^{\circ}/7$ mm., yield 14 g. (Found : N, 10.91. $C_{13}H_{20}O_3N_2$ requires N, 11.1 per cent).

Ethyl α -Cyano- β -(γ -ethoxypropyl)-crotonate.—A mixture of γ -ethoxypropylmethyl ketone (15 g.), ethyl cyanoacetate (11.3 g.), acetamide (2 g.) and glacial acetic acid (24 c.c.) was taken in a flask fitted with a fractionating column and directly heated over a small flame. The temperature was so maintained that acetic acid (24 c.c.) distilled off in about 3-4 hours. The residue was cooled, diluted with water, extracted with ether and washed with sodium bicarbonate. From the ethereal solution the unsaturated ester was isolated, b.p. $135^{\circ}/5$ mm., yield 20 g. (Found : N, 6.3. $C_{12}H_{18}O_3N$ requires N, 6.2 per cent).

Ethyl $\alpha\beta$ -Dicyano- β -(γ -ethoxypropyl)-butyrate (VI).—To a solution of the foregoing unsaturated cyano-ester (11 g.) in alcohol (95%, 60 c.c.) was added potassium cyanide (65 g. in 35 c.c. of water). The mixture became warm and was cooled in ice. Next water (35 c.c.), and hydrochloric acid (d 1.15, 8 c.c.) were added with cooling. After standing for 20 minutes at ordinary temperature the reaction mixture was poured into 250 c.c. of ice-cold dilute hydrochloric acid. The precipitated heavy oil was extracted with ether, dried and distilled, yield 10.5 g., b.p. 167-69°/6 mm. (Found : N, 11.6. $C_{13}H_{20}O_3N$ requires N, 11.1 per cent).

Ethyl α -Methyl- α -(γ -ethoxypropyl)-succinate.—The above dicyano-ester (45 g.) was hydrolysed with dilute sulphuric acid (108 c.c. in 360 c.c. of water) for 72 hours, when most of the oil went into solution. After saturation with ammonium sulphate, the solution was thoroughly extracted with ether. The reddish gum (30 g.), obtained from ether, was dried in vacuum and esterified by refluxing for 24 hours with a mixture of alcohol (200 c.c.) and sulphuric acid (30 c.c., d 1.84). After working up in the usual way, it was collected at 134°/5 mm., yield 26 g. (Found : C, 61.3 ; H, 9.05. $C_{14}H_{26}O_6$ requires C, 61.3 ; H, 9.4 per cent).

It may be mentioned that the use of sulphuric acid of higher concentration for hydrolysis resulted in the decomposition of the product.

Ethyl $\alpha\delta$ -Dibromovalerate (VII, R=H).—Ethyl γ -bromopropylmalonate (26 g.) was hydrolysed with hydrobromic acid (48%, 100 c.c.) for 8 hours. After dilution with water, the heavy layer was extracted with ether and the extract dried in vacuum for several days after removal of the solvent. It was subsequently treated with thionyl chloride (8 c.c.) and then heated on the water-bath for about 2 hours until the initial reaction was over. After cooling, bromine (8 c.c.) was gradually added to the mixture and it was left overnight at ordinary temperature ; after which it was heated for a day with additions of bromine until the colour persisted. The mixture was then treated with alcohol (50 c.c.) and refluxed for 2 hours. After working up in the usual way, it was collected at 111-12°/5 mm., yield 19 g. (Found : Br, 55.1. $C_7H_{12}O_2 Br_2$ requires Br, 55.5 per cent).

Ethyl 1-Cyano-cyclopentane-1 : 2-dicarboxylate (VIII).—The foregoing dibromo-ester (19 g.), diluted with a little alcohol, was added slowly to a well-cooled suspension of ethyl sodiocyanoacetate in alcohol, prepared from cyanoacetic ester (15 g., 2 mols), 3.3 g. of sodium (2 mols) and alcohol (50 c.c.). Considerable amount of heat was evolved and the alcohol began to boil. After standing at ordinary temperature overnight, the mixture was refluxed over a free flame for 24 hours. The product was poured into water, extracted with ether and the extract was thoroughly washed with water, when most of the colour was removed. The residue was worked

up in the usual way and then distilled in vacuum, the fraction b.p. 130-42°/4 mm. being collected, yield 11.5 g. On redistillation practically the whole of it passed over at 132°/3 mm. as a colourless viscous oil (Fuson, *loc. cit.*, records b.p. 135-36°/3.5 mm. for this compound). (Found: C, 60.1; H, 6.8. Calc. for $C_{12}H_{17}O_4N$: C, 60.2; H, 6.7 per cent).

The above cyano-ester was hydrolysed according to Fuson (*loc. cit.*), when a substance, m.p. 153-58°, evidently crude cyclopentane-1: 2-dicarboxylic acid, was isolated. This was converted into the anhydride of the *cis*-form by refluxing with acetic anhydride for 7 hours, whereby it was obtained as a gelatinous mass boiling at 100°/4 mm. This, on boiling with water gave the pure *cis*-acid, m.p. 141°.

Ethyl α -Methyl- α -carbethoxy- δ -bromovalerate.—To ethyl sodiomethylmalonate, prepared in benzene solution by the gradual addition of ethyl methylmalonate (50 g.) to finely powdered sodium (6 g.), trimethylene bromide (60 g.) was added and the mixture refluxed on the water-bath for 16 hours. After working up in the usual way, the fraction boiling at 150-75°/14 mm. was collected and redistilled at 153-55°/12 mm., yield 28 g. (Found: Br, 27.0. $C_{11}H_{18}O_4Br$ requires Br, 27.1 per cent).

Ethyl $\alpha\delta$ -Dibromo- α -methylvalerate (VII, R=Me).—The above ester (25 g.) was hydrolysed with hydrobromic acid (48%, 150 c.c.) by refluxing over a free flame for 16 hours. On the addition of water, a heavy oil separated at the bottom, which was extracted with ether. After removal of the solvent, the residual liquid was dried over potassium hydroxide for 2 days, yield 12 g. This product (18 g.) was treated with phosphorus pentabromide and the mixture allowed to stand for 4 hours at the ordinary temperature. Bromine (8 c.c.) was added and the mixture left overnight. It was heated on the water-bath for 12 hours with the addition of a further quantity of bromine until the colour persisted. Then it was poured into absolute alcohol (125 c.c.) with ice-cooling. After refluxing for 2 hours it was worked up in the usual way, b.p. 118-20°/6.5 mm., yield 24 g. (Found: Br, 50.0. $C_8H_{14}O_2Br_2$ requires, Br, 50.3 per cent).

Ethyl 1-Cyano-2-methyl-cyclopentane-1: 2-dicarboxylate (IX).—The above dibromo compound (23 g.) was added to ethyl sodiocyanacetate, prepared from ethyl cyanacetate (17 g.), sodium (3.6 g.) and alcohol (55 c.c.), when the initial vigour of the reaction subsided, it was refluxed over a free flame for 30 hours. The product was worked up as before and the fraction, b.p. 110-22°/1 mm., collected and redistilled at 118-20°/1 mm., yield 15.5 g. (Found: C, 61.3; H, 7.5. $C_{13}H_{19}O_4N$ requires C, 61.6; H, 7.5 per cent).

trans-1-Methylcyclopentane-1: 2-dicarboxylic Acid (I).—The above cyano-ester (6 g.) was hydrolysed with fuming hydrochloric acid (35 c.c.)

over a free flame for 30 hours, then concentrated and cooled when crystalline precipitate separated. The crude acid had m. p. 137-39°. On crystallising from water, it was obtained in beautiful radiating cubes, m. p. 143°, the mixed m. p. with the acid obtained previously showed no depression. (Found : C, 55.9 ; H, 6.8. $C_8H_{12}O_4$ requires C, 55.8 ; H, 6.9 per cent).

cis-1-Methylcyclopentane-1 : 2-dicarboxylic Acid (I).—8 G. of the above cyano-ester (X) was heated in a sealed tube with fuming hydrochloric acid (35 c.c.) for 3 hours at 160° and at 180° for 9 hours. The mixture (slight tar formed) was extracted with ether and the residue from ether was repeatedly charcoaled in aqueous solution. Some difficulty was experienced in crystallisation, for it evidently consisted of a mixture of *cis*- and *trans*-forms. Ultimately the solution was very slowly cooled after the addition of a few drops of hydrochloric acid and the separated mixture had m.p. 107-128°. (Found : C, 56.08 ; H, 6.56. $C_8H_{12}O_4$ requires C, 55.8, H, 6.9 per cent).

The mixture (2 g.) was refluxed with acetic anhydride (20 c.c.) for 10 hours and after removal of the latter, the anhydride was obtained as a gelatinous mass showing a tendency to crystallisation and b p. 101°/4 mm., yield 1.1 g. A residue also remained in the flask. The anhydride was refluxed with dilute hydrochloric acid for 7 hours. On concentrating the solution, a sandy crystalline powder separated. This was recrystallised from water containing hydrochloric acid, when it was obtained as clusters of small cubes. A fresh sample dried over a porous plate showed m. p. 124-26° with previous softening at 120°, but after drying in *vacuo* over sulphuric acid for a week had m. p. 120-25°. (Found : C, 56.3 ; H, 6.4. $C_8H_{12}O_4$ requires C, 55.8 ; H, 6.9 per cent).

Conversion of the trans-Acid into cis-form and vice versa.—The pure acid (10 g., m. p. 142°) was heated with fuming hydrochloric acid (15 c.c.) at 190-200° for 12 hours. The separated solid was collected with adhering tarry matter and repeatedly treated with animal charcoal in aqueous solution until colourless. The solution was allowed to crystallise slowly after the addition of a little hydrochloric acid. The m. p. of successive crops was indefinite between 120 and 135° showing thereby that the *trans*-acid was contaminated with the *cis*-isomer. Similarly when 3 g. of the *cis*-acid were treated under similar conditions, the product was found to melt within 5° of the value recorded for that of the pure *cis*-acid (124-26°).

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